

The CHANGE Project: Comparing the sizes of ancient bronze coinages

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The CHANGE project, subtitled ‘The development of the monetary economy of ancient Anatolia, c. 630-30 BC’, is an ERC Consolidator project, designed to take a very broad, data-driven look at the monetary history of this period and region.² We may divide the data we are looking at into four different categories. First there is the basic typology of the coinage produced. For this we have harnessed a Linked Open Data approach that allows us to reuse and enrich the typologies produced by other projects. These are the Corpus Nummorum project (<https://www.corpus-nummorum.eu>) which covers the regions of Mysia and Troas, the Hellenistic Royal Coinages project (<https://numismatics.org/hrc/>), which covers the Macedonian, Seleucid and Ptolemaic royal coinages produced in Asia Minor, and the IRIS typology (<https://greekcoinage.org/iris>), produced by the ARCH project with a view to filling the gaps between the other two (<http://greekcoinage.org/arch>). We have expanded these typologies in certain areas and are enriching them with two further categories of data. First there is the hoard evidence. This has been the focus of the work of one of the postdoctoral researchers on the project, Dr Leah Lazar, who has created a database of hoards found in Anatolia, or found elsewhere but containing coins of Anatolia, based on the data already within the coinhoards.org platform (itself drawn from *IGCH*), supplemented with the data from the 10 first volumes of *Coin Hoards*. Second, there is the evidence from published excavations. This has too has been the responsibility of Dr Lazar, and is discussed elsewhere in this volume. The fourth category of data is epigraphic. There is, needless to say, a major corpus of epigraphic material now published from across Anatolia, which has much, potentially, to tell us about the development of the use of money and coinage across time and space. This area of research has been the responsibility of a second researcher on the project, Dr Marcus Chin, who has now produced a massive database of epigraphic evidence (<https://change.csad.ox.ac.uk/inscriptions>), and who also presents some preliminary results in his paper in this volume.

In this paper I will focus on the first of these projects, the typology, and one particular aspect of its use that I want to begin to test.

The Change project is funding the digitisation and cataloguing of the collections of the British Museum and the Staatliche Münzkabinett in Berlin, and in addition to this is assigning typological identifiers to the collections in Ashmolean Museum in Oxford and the royal collection in Copenhagen. Since the collection in Paris was already catalogued as part of the ARCH project, this means that the Asia Minor typology will, when complete, link to examples in five ‘universal’ collections.

Partly, of course, this decision was taken for practical reasons: it gives a good chance of providing a high coverage of illustrated specimens, as well as serving as a check that we have included the majority of known types. But there is also research potential here. Simply put, the question I asked in the bid for funding was, ‘Could the figures for the numbers of coins be used as a proxy for original size of coinage. Could this be used a short-cut towards quantification of ancient coinages, and particularly of bronze coinages, when die studies do not exist?’ This

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seems, at first glance a risky enterprise, and this is intentional: CHANGE was conceived as a high-risk, high-gain research project, and this seems like a good case of such a proposition. Here is how it was justified in the grant proposal:

“A key component will be an attempt comparatively to quantify ancient coin production over the whole of Anatolia across six centuries. This will be attempted by using the numbers of coins in the five core collections mentioned above as a proxy for the original sizes of the coinages in question. Methodologically speaking, this is a high-risk approach. There is a danger that any given collection may be skewed in some way that is likely to distort its representation of coinage with regard to original sizes of issues. A collection formed in Smyrna, for example, may be skewed towards Smyrna or Ionia. A collection formed in the 19th century by an aristocrat may be skewed towards precious metal. A collection formed by a poorer man in the 20th century may be more skewed towards base-metal coinage. To counter such potential bias, the five core collections for the CHANGE project have been chosen because they do not reside within the source area (Anatolia), and should be free from regional bias, nor were they formed there. They are also all collections with long histories, with their origins at different points in the 18th or 19th centuries, so should be free of consistent temporal bias. Finally, by choosing five collections, the danger that a single major donor has skewed a particular sample is mitigated. At the very least it will hopefully be possible to produce a ranking of output of issuing authorities, broken down by material, denomination and date, which can be exploited to analyse relative production patterns across time and space.”

Such an approach is not, of course, new, and has been attempted before with varying degrees of success. The authors of *Roman Provincial Coinage*, for example, noted in the introduction to their first volume that correlations between sizes of issues and representation in museum collections did not look encouraging. Examining the case of Antioch in the reign of Nero, they concluded, ‘there is not a good correlation between size of issue and its representation in museums. Museum collections are least representative when very few coins were minted (i.e., rarities are over-represented in museums) or, conversely, when very few types were minted in large quantities. When more varied types were minted (years 3-5 and especially years 13- 14, when the types were interesting), museum collections are better represented than in other plentiful years.’³ At this level of specificity (annual issues), there may be problems. On the other hand, an attempt to compare much broader sections of coinage from the later Roman Empire across five museum collections by Andrei Gandila has produced more promising results: ‘there is a striking resemblance between the five major collections in terms of structure and consequently, of statistical results.... What counts in the end is the observable similarity of these collections, even when they are tested at the detailed level of annual fluctuations.... Such statistical similarities indirectly underscore acceptable degree of randomness in the large collections under consideration.’⁴

In the discussion that follows I aim to test the feasibility of using numbers of coins in the five CHANGE core collections by comparing the figures for a number of mints for which die-studies exist. Crucially, since die studies now exist for a significant number of silver coinages (thus obviating the need for the proxy approach), and since the results of these die studies are now readily available in the SILVER web-resource,⁵ I have chosen here to focus on bronze

³ Burnett, Amandry and Ripollès 1992, I: 56.

⁴ Gandila 2009: 161-2. His five collections are the Dumbarton Oaks and the Whittemore collection, the Bibliothèque Nationale in Paris, the British Museum, the collection Köhler-Osbahr in Duisburg and the American Numismatic Society.

⁵ Available at https://silver.knowledge.wiki/Die_Studies_Database. For discussion of the project see Callataÿ [BELOW – Cross ref to Callataÿ paper].

coinages for which both specimen numbers and die-studies exist. For eight of these the studies that have been conducted have involved collection of what we may term a ‘global’ specimen set (i.e. including many collections, as well as commerce), and since they list their sources it has been possible to segregate the specimens from the five CHANGE core collections, to compare the results of die-study with both the ‘Global’ specimen count and the ‘Core-5’ specimen count. For one dataset, it has not been possible to segregate the Core-5 specimens, so I have just worked with the Global figure. Finally, I have added a further data set which has no die-study but does have Global and Core-5 specimen numbers, to provide a test-case of the CHANGE proposition that we might use such numbers in isolation as a proxy for size. The datasets are summed up in Fig. 1.

Mint	Source	Global	Core-5	Die-study
Sardis	Hochard 2020	x	x	x
Thyateira	Hochard 2020	x	x	x
Mostene	Hochard 2020	x	x	x
Apollonis	Hochard 2020	x	x	x
Hieracome	Hochard 2020	x	x	x
Magnesia ad Sipylum	Hochard 2020	x	x	x
Philadelphia	Hochard 2020	x	x	x
Alabanda	Meadows forthcoming a	x	x	x
Eumeneia	Ünal 2014	x		x
Aegae, Aeolis	Meadows forthcoming b	x	x	

Fig. 1. Data sets utilized in this study

In order to compare the relative sizes of coinages on the basis of numbers surviving compared to dies observed⁶ I have ranked the types within their individual mints in terms first of numbers of specimens observed (highest to lowest) in the global dataset (n) and Core-5 dataset (c), and then in terms of dies observed (highest to lowest) (d). The tables containing the raw data for the ten mints tested are provided in the appendix below (Data Tables 1-10). Since the primary concern is to investigate rank orders of magnitude, and an approach that compares rankings has been chosen. To compare the resulting rankings, I have used Spearman’s Rank correlation coefficient (ρ), where 1 = a perfect correlation, and 0 = no correlation (Fig. 2).

⁶ In this study I have used observed dies rather than estimates of original numbers on the basis of statistical formulae, since in many cases sample sizes are too small for reliable use of such statistical methods. There is an inevitable risk in this, of course, which must be borne in mind in interpretation of results. By presenting all relevant numbers in the tables that follow I aim at least to be transparent in this respect.

<p>Formula</p> $\rho = 1 - \frac{6 \sum d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}$ <p> ρ = Spearman's rank correlation coefficient d_i = difference between the two ranks of each observation n = number of observations </p>
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Fig 2. Spearman's Rank Coefficient

By comparing the rankings (ρ) we may assess the usefulness of using the different measures (n) and (c) as proxies for (d) in determining the relative sizes of different coinages. There are obviously a number of different comparisons are possible, and I will proceed in what follows to begin to test which, if any, of these appear fruitful. I will start by looking at the relationship between (n) and (c) - the global vs. the core datasets, with a view to seeing if there are grounds to believe that (c) might be useful. I will then move towards a detailed examination of production within each mint, to see if (n) and (c) can be used as proxies for the size of different types within a mint's overall production.⁷ Finally, I will take a step back and ask if (n) and (c) can be used as proxies for the overall size of mints, thereby allowing the establishment of a rank order of coin production centres in Asia Minor in the period 200-30 BC.⁸

1. Assessing the Core-5 representation

The availability of figures for Global collections (n) of data alongside figures for the Core-5 collections (c) obviously offers the opportunity to assess the correlation between the two samples. If we compare the rankings of Global vs. Core-5 samples for the coinages of the nine mints for which this is possible, the following results emerge (Fig. 3).

Mint	ρ of n and c
Sardis	0.96
Thyateira	0.97
Mostene	1
Apollonis	0.95
Hieracome	0.66
Magnesia ad Sipylum	0.94

⁷ For these purposes the definition of type adopted by the CHANGE project is used, viz. a typologically distinct group, rather than individual issues within such a group that are distinguished by control differences. This is thus a slightly broader concept than that adopted by the RPC project.

⁸ Given the uncertainty of the chronology of many of the bronze coinages produced during this period, for the purposes of this paper it seems best to begin with a broad period of analysis.

Philadelphia	0.92
Alabanda	0.71
Aegae	0.98

Fig 3. ρ of n and c

It is immediately apparent that for the majority of mints the correlation is excellent. In general, it appears safe to use the numbers of coins present in the Core-5 collections to determine the relative size of coinages within the overall production of mints that are well represented there. The two exceptions to this rule, Hieracome, and to a lesser extent Alabanda, are probably to be explained by their relatively poor representation in Core-5. For Hieracome there are only 7 specimens in Core-5, and the majority of types are represented by just a single specimen, making it impossible, in fact, to rank them (see Appendix, Data-Table 5). For Alabanda (Data-Table 8) there are similarly low numbers of specimens in the Core-5 for a significant proportion of types, again making ranking impossible.

With reasonable confidence, and with the caveats just noted, therefore, we may proceed to compare the Core-5 and Global rankings with observed numbers of dies to see how well these correlate.

2. Comparing Core-5 and Global specimen numbers to observed dies within mints

In our next table (Fig. 4) we may thus compare the size rankings for the coinages of nine mints in terms of the observed dies (d) vs. first n and then, where available, c.

Mint	ρ of n and d	ρ of c and d	n/type	c/type	n
Mostene	1	1	6	4	13
Eumeneia	1		81		406
Thyateira	0.96	0.88	13	6	65
Sardis	0.94	0.88	39	16	389
Alabanda	0.92	0.66	12	3	216
Apollonis	0.67	0.85	10	4	39
Hieracome	0.67	1	2.6	1	13
Philadelphia	0.52	0.56	16	7	129
Magnesia ad Sipyllum	0.49	0.58	6	4	56

Fig. 4. Correlation of rankings of n and d and c and d compared

There is obviously some ‘noise’ in these results. A number of mints are represented by less than 50 specimens (n) in total (Mostene, Hieracome and Apollonis), and these samples are probably too small to be usable. But, since we are ranking these mints in terms of their types, it is important also to look at the relative representation of these (n/type and c/type). Here we see that all but one of the coinages that have an n/type of 12 or greater yield a correlation of n to

d of 0.92 or better.⁹ In these cases it looks like we may take numbers of coins per type as a good proxy for original relative sizes of issues within a mint. On the other hand, within our sample only one mint achieves that level of representation within the core collections, and it must be admitted that the current choice of core collections probably do not offer a clear method of determining relative sizes of coinages within a mint. An increase in number of core collections may solve this problem, but most probably this will be best achieved by incorporating the bronze coins that now appear online in commerce with increasing frequency.

3. Comparing mints

If the core collections do not in general allow us to compare production within mints, can they be used instead to compare the relative sizes of mint output?

Mint	n	c	d	n rank	c rank	d rank	n/d	c/d
Sardis	389	165	65	1	1	2	5.98	2.54
Alabanda	216	61	143	2	2	1	1.51	0.43
Philadelphia	129	60	20	3	3	3	6.45	3.00
Magnesia ad Sipylum	56	32	18	5	4	4	3.11	1.78
Thyateira	65	28	16	4	5	5	4.06	1.75
Apollonis	39	16	8	6	6	6	4.88	2.00
Mostene	13	8	5	7	7	8	2.60	1.60
Hieracome	13	7	8	7	8	6	1.63	0.88

Fig. 5. Relative sizes of coinages by n, c and d with ratios of n/d and c/d

In Fig. 5 we see the result of looking just at the global figures for each mint of numbers of observed dies (d), global specimens (n) and Core 5 specimens (c) and ranking them in descending order. As is clear from a glance, the correlation is extremely good. In fact, ρ for both n and d and c and is 0.92. There is very close correlation across all three measures. This provides good grounds for suggesting that any one of these measures in isolation is likely to be a good guide to the others, and we may thus add back in to our data set the results for Eumeneia for which we have no Core figure (c) and Aegae for which we have no die study (d), and rank all ten mints by the one figure we have for all (n) (Fig. 6).

Mint	n	c	d
Eumeneia	406		146
Sardis	389	165	65
Aegae	288	129	
Alabanda	216	61	143
Philadelphia	129	60	20
Thyateira	65	28	16
Magnesia ad Sipylum	56	32	18

⁹ The exception is Philadelphia which has 8 types represented by 129 specimens. Closer inspection of its data table (Appendix, Data-Table 7) shows a significant variation of representation among these types, which may be the cause of its unexpectedly low correlation.

Apollonis	39	16	8
Hieracome	13	7	8
Mostene	13	8	5

Fig 6. Sizes of samples (*n* and *c*) and observed dies by Mint

Both Eumeneia and Aegae seem to take their appropriate places in the table: Eumeneia in first place on the basis of both *n* and *d*, and Aegae in third on the basis both of *n* and *c*. We are thus presented with a comparison of output of ten mints across the period c. 200-30 BC, within which all of these coinages are conventionally dated. We should be aware, of course, that the date ranges of production may vary. The issues of Mostene, for example, are placed by Hochard between c. 100 and c. 30 BC, while those of Alabanda probably span the whole of the period. Nonetheless, we begin here to see an index of relative output of production of bronze coinage in the 2nd and 1st centuries BC. We may also begin to visualize this in new ways (Fig. 8). There is, moreover, strong reason to believe that further collection and comparison of data can lead us to a broader reconstruction and interpretation of the shift towards fiduciary coinage that took place in this period.

Fig. 7. Relative sizes of mints (*n*), c. 200-30 BC

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Appendix. Data Tables

URI	From	To	Obverse Type	Reverse Type	d	n	c	n/d	c/d	d rank	n rank	c rank
sardes_hochard_2020_4.7	-200	-30	Bust of Cybele wearing a turreted crown	Zeus holding eagle and sceptre	6	33	13	5.50	2.17	4	4	5
sardes_hochard_2020_4.8.1827	-200	-30	Head of Dionysus wearing a vine wreath	Forepart of lion roaring	1.5	24	11	16.00	7.33	7	6	6
sardes_hochard_2020_4.8.1828	-200	-30	Head of Dionysus wearing a vine wreath	Panther with horns, head facing	3.5	31	14	8.86	4.00	6	5	4
sardes_hochard_2020_4.8.1829-33	-200	-30	Head of Dionysus in a diadem	Demeter, draped with sceptre	1	7	5	7.00	5.00	8	8	7
sardes_hochard_2020_4.9.1834	-200	-30	Head of Heracles in a lion's skin	Kantharos (wine vase)	4	17	5	4.25	1.25	5	7	7
sardes_hochard_2020_4.9.1835-6	-200	-30	Bust of Heracles in laurel wreath and lion skin	Apollo with bird and lyre; laurel wreath	1	7	4	7.00	4.00	8	8	9
sardes_hochard_2020_4.9.1837-57	-200	-30	Bust of Heracles in laurel wreath and lion skin	Apollo with bird and lyre; laurel wreath	20	128	40	6.40	2.00	1	1	2
sardes_hochard_2020_4.9.1858-9	-200	-30	Bust of Heracles in laurel wreath and lion skin	Lion; in the upper field, a bee	1	5	3	5.00	3.00	8	10	10
sardes_hochard_2020_4.10	-200	-30	Head of Apollo in a laurel wreath	Club in an oak wreath	17	94	51	5.53	3.00	2	2	1
sardes_hochard_2020_4.11	-200	-30	Bust of Artemis	Athena dressed in chiton holding Nike	10	43	19	4.30	1.90	3	3	3
					65	389	165	6.98	3.37			

1. Sardis

URI	From	To	Obverse Type	Reverse Type	d	n	c	n/d	c/d	d rank	n rank	c rank
thyatira_hochard_2020_2.1.2359	-200	-100	Head of Apollo in laurel wreath	Double axe	12	49	19	4.08	1.58	1	1	1
thyatira_hochard_2020_2.1.2360	-200	-100	Head of Apollo in laurel wreath	Double axe	1.5	10	4	6.67	2.67	2	2	2
thyatira_hochard_2020_2.1.2361	-200	-100	Bust of Artemis Boreitene draped	Apollo holding bow and arrow	1	3	3	3.00	3.00	3	3	3
thyatira_hochard_2020_2.1.2362	-200	-100	Bust of Artemis Boreitene draped	Stag	1	2	1	2.00	1.00	3	4	4
thyatira_hochard_2020_2.1.2363	-200	-100	Bust of Artemis Boreitene draped	Bow and quiver	0.5	1	1	2.00	2.00	5	5	4
					16	65	28	3.55	2.05			

2. Thyateira

URI	From	To	Obverse Type	Reverse Type	d	n	c	n/d	c/d	d rank	n rank	c rank
mostene_hochard_2020_1.1	-100	-30	Head of Zeus in a laurel wreath	Apollo Tyrimnos on horseback	4	7	5	1.75	1.25	1	1	1
mostene_hochard_2020_1.2	-100	-30	Female head in a veil and stephane	Corn-ear in a corn wreath	1	6	3	6.00	3.00	2	2	2
					5	13	8	3.88	2.13			

3. Mostene

URI	From	To	Obverse Type	Reverse Type	d	n	c	n/d	c/d	d rank	n rank	c rank
apollonis_hochard_2020_2.2	-200	-30	Macedonian shield with stars	Club	1	13	4	13	4	3	2	2
apollonis_hochard_2020_2.3	-200	-30	Head of Tyche wearing a turreted crown	Zeus seated holding sceptre and eagle	2	9	4	4.5	2	2	3	2
apollonis_hochard_2020_2.1	-200	-30	Head of Heracles in lion's skin	Winged thunderbolt	4	15	7	3.75	1.75	1	1	1
apollonis_hochard_2020_2.4	-200	-30	Head of Zeus wearing a laurel wreath	Caduceus	1	2	1	2	1	3	4	3
Total/Average					8	39	16	5.81	2.19			

4. Apollonis

URI	From	To	Obverse Type	Reverse Type	d	n	c	n/d	c/d	d rank	n rank	c rank
hieracome_hochard_2020_2.1	-100	-30	Head of Apollo w. laurel wreath	Bow and quiver in laurel wreath	1	1	1	1	1	2	4	2
hieracome_hochard_2020_2.2	-100	-30	Bust of Apollo	Forepart of a deer kneeling	4	7	3	1.75	0.75	1	1	1
hieracome_hochard_2020_2.3	-100	-30	Bust of Artemis	Forepart of a deer kneeling	1	2	1	2.00	1.00	2	2	2
hieracome_hochard_2020_2.4	-100	-30	Bust of Artemis draped	Forepart of a deer kneeling	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	2	4	2
hieracome_hochard_2020_2.5	-100	-30	Male head in a Persian headdress	Artemis seizing stag by horns	1	2	1	2.00	1.00	2	2	2
Totals/averages					8	39	16	1.55	0.95			

5. Hieracome

URI	From	To	Obverse Type	Reverse Type	d	n	c	n/d	c/d	d rank	n rank	c rank
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1037	-200	-100	Head of Zeus in laurel wreath	Demeter, draped with a sceptre	1	3	1	3.00	1.00	4	6	7
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1038	-200	-100	Head of Zeus in laurel wreath	Snake on omphalos	2	5	3	2.50	1.50	3	5	4
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1039	-200	-100	Head of Zeus in laurel wreath	Bunch of grapes	1	2	2	2.00	2.00	4	7	6
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1040-1	-200	-100	Head of Cybele in turreted crown	Zeus Lydios with sceptre and bird	5	10	6	2.00	1.20	1	2	2
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1042	-200	-100	Head of Heracles	Zeus Lydios w. sceptre and bird	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	4	8	7
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1043	-200	-100	Head of Heracles	Athena in Corinthian helmet, shield and bird	1	18	10	18.00	10.00	4	1	1
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1044	-200	-100	Head of Apollo in laurel wreath	Tripod	1	8	3	8.00	3.00	4	3	4
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1045	-200	-100	Head of Apollo in laurel wreath	Horse	1	1	0	1.00	0.00	4	8	9
magnesia_ad_sipylum_hochard_2020_1.1046	-200	-100	Head of Artemis in stephane (crown)	Zeus and Hermes face to face	5	8	6	1.60	1.20	1	3	2
						56	32	4.34	2.32			

6. Magnesia ad Sipylum

URI	From	To	Obverse Type	Reverse Type	d	n	c	n/d	c/d	d rank	n rank	c rank
philadelpheia_lydia_hochard_2020_1.1	-200	-100	Macedonian shield	Thunderbolt in a laurel wreath	3	42	17	14.00	5.67	3	1	1
philadelpheia_lydia_hochard_2020_1.2	-200	-100	Head of Dionysus in a vine wreath	Panther turning head, a thyrsus on its shoulder	1	10	5	10.00	5.00	5	5	5
philadelpheia_lydia_hochard_2020_1.3.1374_76_79	-200	-100	Bust of Artemis in a diadem	Apollo holding a kithara (lyre)	4	17	8	4.25	2.00	2	3	3
philadelpheia_lydia_hochard_2020_1.3.1375_77_78	-200	-100	Bust of Artemis in a stephane	Apollo holding a kithara seated on a throne	3	10	5	3.33	1.67	3	5	5
philadelpheia_lydia_hochard_2020_1.3.1380	-200	-100	Head of Zeus in a diadem	Lyre and plectrum in a laurel wreath	2	26	11	13.00	5.50	4	2	2
philadelpheia_lydia_hochard_2020_1.3.1381	-200	-100	Head of Zeus in a diadem	Apollo Tyrimnos on horseback	1	1	1	1.00	1.00	5	7	8
philadelpheia_lydia_hochard_2020_2.1	-100	-30	Head of Dionysus in a vine wreath	Thyrsus	1	8	5	8.00	5.00	5	7	5
philadelpheia_lydia_hochard_2020_2.2	-100	-30	Heads of the Dioscuri jugate	Pilei topped with stars	5	15	8	3.00	1.60	1	4	3
					20	129	60	7.07	3.43			

7. Philadelphia

URI	From	To	Obverse Type	Reverse Type	d	n	c	n/d	c/d	d rank	n rank	c rank
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.1.1	-205	-200	Head of Apollo	Zebu charging	7	10	7	1.43	1.00	7	7	3
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.1.2	-205	-200	Head of Apollo	Zebu forepart	6	6	5	1.00	0.83	10	13	7
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.1.3	-205	-200	Head of Apollo	Zebu standing	3	4	2	1.33	0.67	15	16	12
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.1.4	-205	-200	Head of Apollo	Zebu standing	4	5	1	1.25	0.25	13	15	16
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.2.1	-200	-190	Head of Apollo	Pegasus	15	25	5	1.67	0.33	3	3	5
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.2.2	-200	-190	Head of Apollo	Pegasus forepart	8	10	1	1.25	0.13	6	6	13
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.2.3	-200	-190	Pegasus flying	Raven flying	3	4	1	1.33	0.33	16	17	17
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.2.4	-200	-190	Head of Apollo	Raven standing	5	8	7	1.60	1.40	11	11	4
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.3.1	-190	-185	Head of Apollo	Zebu	25	35	9	1.40	0.36	1	1	1
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.3.2	-190	-185	Head of Apollo	Zebu forepart	18	26	7	1.44	0.39	2	2	2
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.3.3	-190	-185	Chelys (lyre)	Zebu standing	10	17	5	1.70	0.50	5	5	6
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.4.1	-185	-150	Chrysaor on Pegasus	Zebu standing	3	7	1	2.33	0.33	14	12	15
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.4.2	-185	-150	Pegasus flying	Raven flying	14	25	2	1.79	0.14	4	4	9
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.4.3	-185	-150	Head of Apollo	Raven	7	8	1	1.14	0.14	8	9	14
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.5.1	-150	-80	Pegasus flying	Raven flying	1	6	3	6.00	3.00	18	14	8
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.6.1	-80	-30	Head of Apollo	Tripod	7	8	2	1.14	0.29	9	10	11
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.6.2	-80	-30	Pegasus flying	Zebu charging	4	10	2	2.50	0.50	12	8	10
alabanda_meadows_2020_6.6.3	-80	-30	Head of Apollo	Pegasus laurel wreath	2	2	0	1.00	0.00	17	18	18
					142	216	61	1.74	0.59			

8. Alabanda

	From	To			d	n	n/d	n rank	d rank
eumeneia_unal_2014_i	-170	-40	Head of Artemis	Doiuble axe	3	7	2.33	6	6
eumeneia_unal_2014_ii	-170	-40	Head of Mên wearing Phrygian cap	Eight-rayed stary	5	8	1.60	5	5
eumeneia_unal_2014_iii	-170	-40	Head of Tyche wearing a turreted crown	Fire altar	8	22	2.75	4	4
eumeneia_unal_2014_iv	-170	-40	Head of Zeus wearing a laurel wreath	Legend in an oak wreath	58	217	3.74	1	1
eumeneia_unal_2014_v	-170	-40	Bust of Athena wearing a crested Corinthian helmet	Nike holding a wreath and a palm	49	90	1.84	2	2
eumeneia_unal_2014_vi	-170	-40	Bust of Dionysus wearing an ivy wreath	Tripod, double axe with snake and laurel branch	23	62	2.70	3	3
					146	406	2.78		

9. Eumeneia

URI	From	To	Obv. Type	Rev. type	n	c	n rank	c rank
aegae_aeolis.bmc.2	-200	-150	Head of Apollo wearing a laurel wreath	Goat head	114	47	1	1
aegae_aeolis.bmc.10	-200	-30	Head of Apollo wearing a laurel wreath	Goat	29	12	5	5
aegae_sng_munich_363	-200	-30	Head of Athena in crested helmet	Forepart of goat standing	5	2	9	9
aegae_aeolis.bmc.12	-200	-30	Head of Athena wearing a crested Attic helmet	Zeus, naked, standing facing, holding an eagle and a sceptre	31	19	3	2
aegae_aeolis.bmc.14	-200	-30	Head of Athena wearing a crested Attic helmet	Nike holding a palm and a sceptre	39	17	2	3
aegae_aeolis.bmc.15	-200	-30	Head of Athena wearing a crested Attic helmet	Lyre	19	8	6	6
aegae_aeolis.sng.copenhagen.14	-200	-30	Head of Hermes in petasos	Goat	30	14	4	4
aegae_aeolis.sng.copenhagen.15	-200	-30	Head of Zeus with laurel wreath	Apollo standing holding a branch and taenia (head band)	9	4	8	8
aegae_aeolis.sng.copenhagen.7	-200	-30	Head of Athena wearing a crested Attic helmet	Zeus naked, holding an eagle and a sceptre	12	6	7	7
					288	129		

10. Aegae